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Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) and Greater Strategic Effectiveness of Consultancy Services in Tertiary Education Institutions in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) cannot effectively play their role of human capital development through teaching and research work without adequate funding. Many of these institutions in a bid to boost internally generated revenues now embark on income-generating activities through their consultancy services outfits. This paper primarily held discussions on the need and relevance of Consultancy Services in Tertiary Education Institutions in Nigeria. The paper sourced majority of its data from primary sources involving interviews and discussions with stakeholders in the tertiary education sector. The study revealed that consultancy units in tertiary education institutions provide a wide range of services such as training and capacity building programmes via workshops, conferences, seminars; part time programmes, industry collaboration, policy advocacy, printing press, bookshops, amongst others. It further revealed that poor funding, poor management, limited awareness and visibility, bureaucratic bottlenecks, poor staff commitment, corruption as well as insufficient expertise posed serious challenges to the achievement of the goals for which the Consultancy Units are established. Thus, the paper recommended amongst others the need for efficient management, adequate control and regulation, periodic review of income generating activities and the engagement of internal and external auditors for consultancy services of Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs).

Keywords: Consultancy Services, Management, Revenue Generation, Tertiary Institutions,

1. INTRODUCTION

Tertiary education policy today is receiving increasing attention all over the world, Nigeria inclusive. The widespread recognition that tertiary education is a major driver of economic competitiveness in an increasing knowledge-driven global economy has made high-quality tertiary education more important than ever before (Luke, 2013). The imperative for countries is to raise higher-level employment skills to sustain a globally competitive research-base and to improve knowledge dissemination to the benefit of the society.

Generally, tertiary education contributes to social and economic development through four major missions.

- The formation of human capital (primarily through teaching)
- The building of knowledge-base primarily through research and knowledge development)
- The dissemination and use of knowledge (primarily through interaction with knowledge users)
- The maintenance of knowledge (inter-generational storage and transmission of knowledge).

The primary and traditional role of Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) is the transmission of knowledge and the training of the human mind. This major function is closely linked with the second; engaging in basic research activities which could lead to the advancement of knowledge, i.e., making scientific discoveries (Ojo, 1983). From the early history of tertiary education in Nigeria, the goals of manpower development, the development of cultural citizens and the promotion of basic research have been conferred on the university system (Alo, 1991).

The scope and importance of tertiary education have changed significantly. Over forty (40) years ago, tertiary education, which was more commonly referred to as higher education, was what happened in universities. This largely covered teaching and learning requiring high level conceptual skills in the humanities, sciences and social sciences as well as the preparation of students for entry to a limited number of professions such as medicine, engineering and law. Within the period, there were fewer tertiary institutions in the country, while oil revenue was massively and readily available and therefore, the federal government provided all the funding for operations and capital development needs of the institutions (Akinsanya, 2007). As at today, there is a phenomenal growth in the number of tertiary education institutions in Nigeria with the federal government, state governments and even private individuals establishing institutions.

Today, tertiary education is much more diversified and encompasses other institutions such as Polytechnics, Colleges of Education, Technological Institutes and others which provide one form of higher education or the other. Aina and Alaba (1996), posited that these institutions have been created for a number of reasons; to enhance social and geographical access to tertiary education; to provide high level occupational preparation in a more applied and less theoretical way; and to accommodate the growing diversity of qualifications and expectations of school graduates.

As participation in tertiary education has expanded, tertiary education institutions have assumed responsibility for a far wider range of occupational preparation than in the past. As a result, a wide range of professionals – doctors, engineers, lawyers, accountants, bankers, teachers, pharmacists, speech therapists, business managers, marketers, technologists, welders, etc now receive their principal occupational qualification from the Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs). In addition, TEIs are now involved in a wider range of teaching than their traditional degree-level courses.

Many examples abound as TEIs now offer adult education and leisure courses, foundation courses to prepare students for tertiary-level study and short specific occupational courses at sub-degree levels. The challenge of inadequate funding of Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) in Nigeria has become critical revealing largely due to the huge economic problems facing the Nigerian government, made worse by the recent global financial crisis (Uruakpa and Onuoha, 2012). The FGN (2012) worried about the incessant complaints of poor funding of public institutions of learning, advised university managers through the NUC to explore various ways of generating ten percent (10%) of their expected revenue from within and outside their institutions towards solving their finance-related problems rather than depend almost entirely on subsidization by government. Erhagbe (2014), posited that one big challenge facing university education today in Nigeria is gross under funding which could be linked to undue reliance on Government for funds by university administrators.

Based on this background, many Nigerian Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) now engage in a variety of income generating activities and consultancies – guest houses, printing press, poultry, petrol stations, bookshops, workshops, etc. in order to supplement statutory revenues for government. While some of these ventures have been successful and profitable, others (like other public enterprises) have been very poor. Sometimes, the performance of these ventures conflicts with the objectives of tertiary education system -teaching and research. Furthermore, public service traditions as well as inhibitive bureaucratic bottlenecks have ruined many of them. Thus, finding solutions to the financial challenges facing TEI

Administration in Nigeria with their attendant negative effects on the educational system motivated this study.

Therefore, this paper has its major objectives as assessing the relevance of consultancy services in tertiary education institutions in Nigeria, identifying their services and products, challenges as well as proffering solutions on how best to improve consultancy services in Nigeria tertiary education institutions.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The present crises in Nigeria Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) – underfunding and lack of adequate infrastructures and facilities tend to have serious implications for tertiary institution governance. For TEIs to effectively perform their functions, there must be adequate funding (Idialu and Idialu, 2012). The realities of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) of 1986 and general economic deterioration have forced the government to shift grounds in the management of tertiary education in the country. According to Alo (1991), there have been cuts in Nigeria’s tertiary education financing as a result of SAP and these have had severe implications for the effectiveness and efficiency of the tertiary education system in the country. Dwindling resources lead to under-supply of scientific materials, reduction of book supplies and journal subscriptions, abandoned capital projects; lack of physical and structural facilities, etc. The poor state of tertiary education institutions has led to a lot of staff exodus, referred to as “brain-drain” in the system. Other contributory factors to under-funding of Nigerian tertiary education institutions according to Ogbogu (2011) include lack of planning, proliferation of schools and ad-hoc expansion of enrolment, academic versus non-academic employment ratios, etc. Furthermore, major facilities such as library facilities, information management system, laboratories, health services, etc. can no longer be adequately supported.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to assess the relevance of Consultancy Services Units in tertiary education institutions in Nigeria.

Specifically, this study aims at:

1. identifying the pattern of Consultancy Services Units in Tertiary Education Institutions.
2. identifying quality of services and products provided by Consultancy Services Units in Tertiary Education Institutions in Nigeria.
3. identifying the challenges of Consultancy Services Units in Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) in Nigeria.
4. making recommendations and suggestions on how to improve on the activities of Consultancy Services Units of Tertiary Education Institutions (TEIs) in Nigeria in order to achieve the mandate for which they are established.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Theoretical Review

This study considered three related theories in its quest to explain the relevance of consultancy units in Tertiary Education Institutions in Nigeria in the area of revenue generated.

2.1.1 The African Political Economy (APE) Model

This model provides a partial explanation for the behaviour of Tertiary Education Institutions in times of critical funding challenge (Aina, 2002). The focus of the African Political Economy model according to Wangenge-Ouma and Cloete (2008) is on how political, economic and environmental forces shape the situation or context in which Tertiary Education Institutions carry out their primary functions – teaching and research, especially in the face of inadequate funding by the major economic beneficiaries. Thus, this theory helps to explain the realities of the specific political, economic and social environments that confront the country – political instability, debt burden, inflation, inadequate infrastructure, etc. which consistently produce relative cuts in government expenditure, with the higher education sector highly affected. When there is a cut in budget allocations to the sectors, higher education is worst hit (Ndagi, 1983). Furthermore, it is the claim of this model that as the government’s sources of revenue confronts unexpected volatilities year in year out and as political instability and other negative environmental

constraints throw the government into huge economic challenges, the annual budget commitments to the educational sector decline more and more. Thus, in the face of these financial challenges, Tertiary Education Institutions seek legitimate initiatives such as establishing Consultancy Services Units that will help in raising additional revenue (IGR) for the institution's operations. This study is hinged on this theory.

2.1.2 Resource Dependency Theory

This theory postulates that for an organization to survive in the environment in which they operate, management has a role to allocate resources to innovative activities that are required of the organization by external customers and investors (Pfeffer and Salaneik, 2003). Therefore, how management of organizations compete and win external resources and how they deploy them to productive engagements have huge consequences on the continuity of funding sources and the cooperation of the benefactors of the organizations. Funding problems of TEIs are deeply hinged on economic political and social structures and belief system of the people (Wangenge-Ouma and Cloete, 2008). Thus our educational system is subjected to influence within the economic and social sub-systems.

2.1.3 Human Capital Theory

The human capital theory historically has its roots from the work of Adam Smith (1776) "Wealth of Nation". The emphasis here is on how skills and knowledge acquired by the labour force can influence economic growth and development. He further explained that resources spent on education and training of humans are as important as the resources spent on acquiring physical capital and investment. Education can be regarded, according to Sani (2015), as a personal investment. This is because the intention to invest in education and training is the same as the intention to invest in other types of investment, hence, societies and individuals invest in education to get certain benefits at the end of it all. Human capital theory thus explains the availability of resources in higher education system. The theory brings to light the issue of who should finance higher education. Whether the individual that benefits in term of getting higher earnings after acquiring additional level or type of education or the society who benefited in terms of getting good and enlightened workforce, good healthcare, healthy political participation and improved economic growth.

2.2 Empirical Review

Empirical evidence on consultancy services and tertiary education is not extensive, especially in Nigeria. However, the few ones are mainly on IGR and challenges of funding in universities. Some of them include:

Sabastian, Ariolu, Aireuor and Okoedion (2024) attempted a holistic study of the issues associated with internally generated revenue (IGR) in Nigerian universities. The paper elucidated the concept of IGR, management strategies of IGR and problems associated with IGR. It recommended that adequate technology and infrastructure should be put in place to block leakages and competent task force personnel should be appointed over the administration of IGR amongst others.

Ugwumba (2019) focused his study on the identification of the sources and utilization of IGR by Nigerian polytechnics with special reference to Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana. The study's population of 60 was drawn from the staff of the institution, mainly, management team and staff of the bursary department. Descriptive statistics and the chi-square technique were used in data analysis and hypothesis testing. Findings revealed that commercial ventures, alumni fees and rates constituted the major source of IGR to the polytechnic. The study further revealed that IGR of the polytechnic has not been fully developed to provide up to 10% of the funds required for the overall administration of the school as advised by the federal government of Nigeria. The study thus recommended the need for a transformative, accountable and creative leadership to be maintained with a view to solidify the IGR base for effective administration.

Sani (2015) examined the present financial status of universities in Nigeria in order to establish whether there is adequacy or inadequacy of funds to run their operations. The analysis was based on secondary data and covered 2010-2011 academic session while both descriptive and inferential statistics were

employed in the study. The results revealed that university education is still not adequately funded to meet up with the international benchmark and best practices.

Ogbogu (2011) studied the modes of funding Nigerian universities and the implications on performance. The study revealed that academic staff in the universities did not attend workshops and conferences regularly and that there was a drastic reduction in the award of research grants and fellowships all due to lack of funds.

Okojie (2010) in his study investigated the systems and strategies for funding Nigerian universities and observed that some tertiary institutions have done reasonably well in their drive for substantial IGR and have used it to positively change the landscape of the institutions while some were yet to catch up with the vision.

Isaac (2014) in his study on inadequate funding as the bane of tertiary education in Nigeria critically examined the sources of funding higher education, problems and prospects and posited that one way out of this problem was to focus on internally generated revenue projects which can be used for research works and other developmental projects.

3. METHODOLOGY

According to Amaechi and Amara (2005), research design refers to a blueprint which guides the researcher in his scientific inquiry, investigation and analysis. To achieve the objectives of the study, survey and descriptive research design was adopted. The survey approach was used because of its advantages of identifying the attributes of a large population from a small group of individuals, the economy of the design and the rapid approach in data collection (Fowler and Floyd, 1995). It is also comparably easier to explain and to understand (Osuala, 2010).

A major part of the discussions and interviews for the present study were held in Abia State of Nigeria using Abia State Polytechnic, Aba and few other tertiary education institutions, with functional consultancy units. The data collected were analyzed with the aid of descriptive statistics such as tables and percentages. They were used to analyze the responses of the respondents to enable the researcher form an opinion.

4. DISCUSSIONS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Services and Products of Consultancy Service Units of TEIs

In the course of this study, it was discovered generally that consultancy services in Tertiary Education Institutions involve both academic and non-academic activities. Some of these as revealed in this study include:

1. Organizing and hosting conferences, symposia, and seminars to share research findings and best practices with the broader academic and professional communities.
2. Conducting applied research and consultancy projects for external clients, such as government agencies, private organizations, and industry partners.
3. Providing expert advisory services and technical assistance to address specific challenges or issues faced by clients.
4. Organizing and facilitating training programs, workshops, and short courses for professionals and practitioners.
5. Developing and organizing customized educational programmes such as part-time programmes - weekend and distant.
6. Participating in joint research projects with industry partners, often involving the application of academic knowledge and expertise to real-world problems.
7. Commercializing intellectual property and technology developed within the institution, such as licensing patents, copyrights, and trademarks.
8. Collaborating with other academic institutions, both nationally and internationally, to leverage resources and expertise for joint projects and initiatives.

9. Providing consulting and advisory services to policymakers, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations on issues relating to the institution's areas of expertise.
10. Technology Transfer: Facilitating the commercialization of institution-developed technologies, innovations, or intellectual property through licensing, spin-off companies, or joint ventures.
11. Community Engagement: Collaborating with local communities, non-governmental organizations, or grassroots groups on projects that address social, economic, or environmental issues.
12. Entrepreneurial Support: Providing incubation, acceleration, or mentorship programs for student or faculty-led startups and small businesses.
13. Policy Advocacy: Providing advisory services or research-based evidence to inform public policy discussions and decision-making processes.

4.2 Challenges and Problems of Consultancy Services Units of TEIs

Based on this study, the major challenges and problems facing consultancy services units in the achievement of their mandate include amongst others:

1. Poor Funding: Consultancy units often face financial constraints, thus, limiting their ability to invest in resources, infrastructure, and personnel necessary to provide effective consulting services.
2. Bureaucratic Challenges: Tertiary institutions often have complex administrative structures and decision-making processes, which can slow down the process of responding to client requests and delivering consulting services in a timely manner.
3. Poor Regulation and Accountability: Most at times, the activities of these units are not properly regulated by the management of institutions and thus, this gives rise to laxity on the part of its leadership, corruption and lack of accountability.
4. Limited Awareness and Visibility: There is often a lack of awareness among potential clients, both within and outside the institution, about the expertise and services offered by the consultancy units. This can hinder their ability to attract clients and generate revenue as a result of poor patronage from the public.
5. Insufficient Expertise, Specialization and Poor Staff Commitment: Consultancy units may struggle to maintain a diverse pool of experts with specialized knowledge to cater to the diverse needs of clients. This can limit the range and quality of services they can offer. Many at times, staff of these units do not show any commitment mainly due to lack of motivation from the management.
6. Inadequate Resources and Infrastructure: Consultancy units may lack dedicated office spaces, equipment, and support staff and therefore, making it very difficult to provide a professional and efficient consulting experience to clients.
7. Resistance to Commercialization: There may be a cultural bias within the academic community against the commercialization of knowledge and the provision of paid consulting services, which can create resistance and skepticism towards the consultancy unit's performances.
8. Competition from External Consulting Firms: Tertiary institutions may face competition from established private consulting firms, which can have more resources, marketing capabilities, and industry connections to attract clients.
9. Conflict in Balancing Academic and Consulting Priorities: Consultancy units must strike a balance between supporting the academic mission of the institution and generating revenue through consulting services, which can sometimes create tensions and conflicts.
10. Challenges in Maintaining Quality and Consistency: Ensuring consistent quality of consulting services and maintaining high standards can be a significant challenge, mainly when dealing with a diverse range of client needs and expectations.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Basically, the primary role of tertiary education institutions is the building of knowledge base and the formation of human capital through research and teaching. However, as a result of the under-funding of these institutions and acute lack of adequate infrastructures and facilities, many of them now engage in a variety of income-generating venture via Consultancy Units, for example, Training Programmes, Bookshops, Guest Houses, Printing Press amongst others. Some have been successful and profitable while public service rules and inhibitive bureaucratic regulations have ruined others. The activities of TEIs Consultancy Services Units help tertiary institutions in bridging the gap between academia and the wider community, fostering knowledge transfer, applied research, and collaborative partnerships that can benefit both the institution and its stakeholders.

5.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made towards improving the performances of TEIs Consultancy Services Units in Nigeria, based on this study.

1. Proactive and efficient leadership is needed in TEIs Consultancy Services Units. Appointments to the leadership of these units should be based on merit and not on school politics as is the case in several institutions today.
2. There is need for adequate control and regulation of consultancy units in order to ensure that their income generating activities do not conflict with the cardinal objectives of human capital development through research and teaching.
3. Business ventures engaged by consultancy units require close monitoring by the institutions' authorities to ensure accountability and profitability.
4. There is need to enlighten the public, students, parents, host communities, governments, individuals, professional bodies, firms, etc on the services of tertiary education institutions.
5. Academic staff involved in the management of commercial ventures need close monitoring to ensure that teaching and research duties are not neglected.
6. There is also the need for periodic review of income-generating activities of tertiary education institutions so as to overhaul or scrap non-performing activities/ventures where necessary in order not to plunge the institutions into greater financial difficulties.
7. Heads of tertiary institutions should adequately monitor and supervise these income-generating businesses in order to ensure accountability, transparency and profitability.
8. The engagement of internal and external auditors is advised. This is to ensure that the financial statement presented by those who handle these ventures reflect the true financial position of the businesses.

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